

Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of alternative winter salad value chains supplying the United Kingdom

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Comparative LCA of underutilised leafy greens mix with lettuce supply to the UK.
- Conventional, desalinated water use, hydroponics, agroecological systems compared.
- Agroecological leafy greens imported from Azores can have small environmental footprint.
- Conventional lettuce production in UK during summer had however lowest impact.
- Inefficient distribution could undermine any comparative environmental efficiency.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Lettuce is an established food commodity in the UK increasingly facing supply challenges in winter due to adverse weather events and rising energy costs. We investigate whether an agroecologically grown salad mix of lettuce and underutilised leafy greens produced in the Azores, Portugal, could be part of a sustainable solution. We performed a Life Cycle Assessment to compare the environmental impacts of this salad mix with four other value chains for winter salad supply to the UK: conventional open-field lettuce production chains in Spain using (1) current irrigation practices; (2) 100 % desalinated irrigation water; or hydroponic controlled environment agriculture within the UK powered by (3) the national electricity mix; (4) 100 % wind-generated electricity. Results indicated that the leafy-greens agroecological value chain incurred the smallest environmental burdens across 7 to 11 of 16 impact categories studied. Substituting Spanish winter salad supply with agroecological leafy green production in the Azores, if well managed, could reduce many environmental burdens whilst diversifying leafy greens intake. Nevertheless, all winter value chains were associated with larger environmental burdens than conventional open-field production of lettuce in the UK summer, pointing to the importance of seasonal consumption and wider adoption of agroecological techniques to effectively reduce environmental impact.

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1. Introduction

The consumption of salad leaves is popular globally, and in the United Kingdom the average citizen consumed 51 g of fresh leafy salads a week in 2020–2021 (UK Department for Environment, 2023), representing an annual consumption of approximately 178,920 t of fresh leafy salads when adjusted to the whole UK population (FAO, 2023). However, production of lettuce in the UK is now at its lowest in since 1985, due to dropping yields and a large increase in energy costs, making greenhouse-grown lettuce too expensive to produce (Duncan, 2023). Usually, most of the demand for lettuce in the UK is met through imports. In 2021, the UK imported 214 thousand tonnes of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) and chicory (*Cichorium intybus*), with Spain exporting 83 % of that amount, making it the biggest lettuce exporter country to the UK, followed by Italy (7 %) and France (3 %) (FAO, 2023). Nevertheless, imports of lettuce to the UK were also in decline in 2023, due to adverse weather conditions in Morocco and Spain, and high energy costs in other countries that produce lettuce indoors, such as the Netherlands (Evans et al., 2023).

In addition to the fact that salad leaves are a highly wasteful food item in the UK, with 86,000 whole lettuces being thrown away each day in the UK at the consumer level (WRAP, 2022), the production of salad leaves itself carries a high environmental cost. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a quantitative method used to calculate the environmental impacts of the life cycle of a product or service and can go from the extraction of raw materials down to disposal and treatment. It can be used to understand environmental hotspots and potential improvements along the value chain, and to compare different alternatives.

Numerous LCAs that looked at various lettuce production systems have been published, from organic or conventional systems, to open-field or greenhouse. Table 1 provides an overview of existing LCA studies of salad leafy greens that use primary data. As existing literature on LCAs of salad systems does not follow one common LCA approach in terms of system boundaries, impact assessment methods, etc., making comparison of absolute data is difficult. However, where studies have compared different production systems, several findings are common. Firstly, lettuce is the most common salad leafy green studied, and other salad crops are seldom studied. A study that compares another leafy green type (escarole) with lettuce found that escarole was associated with a higher environmental burden due to lower yields (Romero-Gómez et al., 2014). Other studies look at highly technological systems, mostly hydroponics and vertical farming (Barla et al., 2020). The common finding of these studies is that all of these approaches are highly energy intensive, and that the geographical location, as well as the energy mix of the country they are set in, are important in determining environmental sustainability. Moreover, these technological systems require less water than the conventional production methods.

Most studies use a mass-based functional unit, and those that look at organic systems also use a land-based one. When using land-based units, the organic system seems to have a smaller environmental impact than the conventional system, but vice-versa when using mass-based units, mostly because of lower yields (Foteinis and Chatzisyneon, 2016). In greenhouse systems, the infrastructure is a major contributor to the environmental burden of leafy green production across the majority of categories. Results are mixed about what system between greenhouse and open-field has a lower environmental impact. Romero-Gómez et al. (2014) investigated the environmental consequences of different N fertiliser application rates and different cultivation structures, namely plastic greenhouse, mulch, mulch and fleece, and open-field, for escarole and lettuce production systems in Spain. Regardless of the N fertiliser application rate, the greenhouse system was found to have the highest environmental impact due to the materials of the structure itself. Nevertheless, there is space for improvement by using different or less material. On the other side, Bartzas et al. (2015) performed a LCA of open-field and greenhouse cultivation of lettuce in Spain and Italy, and found that the open-field lettuce had a larger climate change burden

than the greenhouse lettuce. Only one study investigated the effect of intercropping versus monocropping and found that intercropping presents environmental benefits, as inputs were shared between the crops (de Jesus Pereira et al., 2021). Most LCA studies are at farm or retail gate, assuming that the later stages are equivalent. Several studies investigate the supply of leafy greens to the UK, highlighting that supplying sustainable salad leaves to this country is of interest (Casey et al., 2022; Hospido et al., 2009; Milà i Canals et al., 2008). No cultivation system is more sustainable across all environmental impact categories. There are always trade-offs. Lastly, for soil-based cultivation systems, only one study looks at a distinct production method than organic or conventional (Tasca et al., 2017).

One study highlighted the high water use of lettuce production in the Spanish region of Murcia, a major World and UK exporter of lettuce and other horticultural crops (Martin-Gorriz et al., 2020), and a later study looked at the use of desalinated water for lettuce production in the same region (Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2023).

A study from Casey et al. (2022) compared the environmental impact of different conventional open-field production systems in the UK and Spain with high-tech hydroponics in the UK. Hydroponics Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA) is a method of cultivation where crops are grown without soil and under specific conditions to achieve desired parameters (Srivani and Manjula, 2019). This technique has recently become increasingly popular, as it offers a highly regulated environment that can potentially tackle some of the pressing issues in the food system. These include excessive greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient pollution due to the use of large external inputs, as well as the degradation of soils and loss of biodiversity through the standardization of monoculture and intensive agricultural practices (Willett et al., 2019). An additional advantage of a hydroponics CEA supply chain is the considerable decrease in distribution distances, with the structure potentially being in town. The authors found that hydroponic CEA systems differed significantly depending on their energy source, and that the overall impact could be significantly reduced if a cleaner electricity grid was used.

Based on the information gathered from our review, our case study adds to previous knowledge by providing the first LCA of an underutilised leafy greens salad mix grown under agroecological conditions, compared with lettuce value chains from different countries. These lettuce value chains, ending at a regional distribution centre in London, include conventional, open-field systems in Spain using freshwater or 100 % desalinated water for irrigation, and a hydroponics supply chain in the UK using the current electricity grid, or 100 % wind generated electricity on grid, as described in Casey et al. (2022).

Agroecological farming is a holistic method that considers the interconnectedness of ecology, health, society, ethics, and economy in food systems, and can lead to improvements in food security and nutrition (Kerr et al., 2021; Wezel et al., 2009). An agroecological system often involves diverse crops through practices such as intercropping, rotation, agroforestry, and the simultaneous production of crops and livestock, as well as careful management of soil health, therefore providing a potentially more sustainable approach to food production (Willett et al., 2019). The farm used in our case study is characterised by the presence of >100 different cultivars grown in rotation or by intercropping, agroforestry, and minimal cultivation of soils to maximise soil health. Knowledge exchange happens through visits, trainings, and seminars. All the work on the farm is manual, has a reduced reliance on synthetic inputs, and the diversity of outputs provide increased nutrition through plants, roots, herbs, and edible flowers. The leafy greens considered in our case study are part of a rotation consisting of lettuce, Swiss chard (*Beta vulgaris* subsp. L. var. *cicla*), golden purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*), garden orache (*Atriplex hortensis*), buck's-horn plantain (*Plantago coronopus*), and ten mustard plants from the Brassica genus, such as tatsoi (*Brassica rapa* subsp. *narinosa*).

Our case study aims to answer the following questions:

Table 1
Existing LCA studies of leafy greens. RDC = regional distribution centre.

Study	Crop	System boundaries	System and geographical area	Functional unit	Main findings
(Milà i Canals et al., 2008)	Lettuce	cradle to consumption	glasshouse (UK) and open-field (Uganda, Spain, UK)	1 kg lettuce on plate	Heated glasshouse production is worse than Spanish imported production across most impacts, including GWP. If imports are air freighted (Uganda to UK), then favourable system is heated glasshouse.
(Ilari and Duca, 2018)	Endive, escarole, chicory	cradle to nursery (seedling production)	greenhouse (Italy)	one small plant in polystyrene tray	Four crops have similar environmental burdens, and escarole is the best performing environmentally due to a shorter growing cycle; main hotspot is plastic material.
(Fusi et al., 2016)	Lettuce	cradle to gate	greenhouse (Italy)	average bag containing 130 g of fresh cut lamb's lettuce	Greenhouse production, and washing and packing are major hotspots.
(Tasca et al., 2017)	Endive	cradle to farm gate and cradle to grave	organic and integrated (Italy)	1 ha of land for one cycle and 1 kg of endive	None of the approaches is absolutely more environmentally sustainable, and organic production needs higher yields and better fertilisation to improve.
(Romero-Gómez et al., 2014)	Lettuce, escarole	cradle to farm gate	unheated greenhouse, plastic mulch combined with fleece, plastic mulch, open-field, with different N fertiliser application rates (Spain)	1 t of Class 1 marketable fresh weight	Regardless of the N fertiliser application rate, the greenhouse system was found to have the highest environmental impact due to the materials of the structure itself. The escarole was also found to be associated with a higher environmental burden than the lettuce crop, due to lower yields.
(Gunady et al., 2012)	Lettuce	cradle to retail	open-field (Australia)	1 kJ of nutritional energy equivalent = 1.38 g	Agriculture machinery operation accounted for more than half of the GWP.
(Bartzas et al., 2015)	Lettuce	cradle to gate	open-field (Italy), greenhouse (Italy, Spain)	1 kg of fresh marketable lettuce	Open-field lettuce had a larger climate change burden than the greenhouse lettuce.
(Foteinis and Chatzisymeon, 2016)	Lettuce	cradle to gate	organic and conventional (Greece)	1 ha of land and 1 t	Organic is more sustainable when using a land based FU, whereas conventional is more sustainable when using a mass based FU.
(Maynard et al., 2023)	Lettuce	cradle-to-store-shelf	local hydroponics CEA, local greenhouse, local seasonal soil, and conventional centralized (US)	1 kg of fresh marketable lettuce	CEA systems have a higher GWP than centralized production but less water use. Local seasonal soil production has a lower GWP than centralized production.
(Hospido et al., 2009)	Lettuce	cradle to regional distribution centre (RDC)	open-field (UK, Spain), greenhouse (UK)	1 kg of lettuce delivered to a UK RDC	Spanish field-grown lettuce imported to the UK had a lower climate change footprint than indoor-produced lettuce grown in the UK during winter. During Summer the UK-grown open-field lettuce had the lowest climate change footprint.
(Plawecki et al., 2014)	Lettuce	cradle to retail	unheated hoop house, open-field (US)	1 kg lettuce	Unheated hoop house lettuce production has smaller environmental footprint than outdoor distant production.
(Hall et al., 2014)	Lettuce	cradle to consumption	industrial and civic scale (Australia)	1 kg lettuce at consumer	Civic production of lettuce had a similar carbon footprint to local industrial production.
(Casey et al., 2022)	Lettuce	cradle to regional distribution centre (RDC)	Hydroponics CEA (UK, South Africa, Norway, on or off-grid, with renewable energy or market mix), open-field (UK, Spain, US, desert)	1 kg of lettuce delivered to a UK RDC	Environmental impacts of hydroponics CEA range from highly unsustainable to comparable to open-field systems, if well designed.
(Barla et al., 2020)	Lettuce	cradle to farm gate	Aeroponics automatic greenhouse during different seasons (Greece)	1 ha, 1 t of lettuce	Aeroponics cultivation during winter had a higher environmental impact. Aeroponic cultivation has a higher environmental impact than soil-based cultivation, due to higher energy use.
(Blom et al., 2022)	Lettuce	cradle to farm gate	Vertical farming, hydroponics greenhouse, and open-field (Netherlands)	1 kg lettuce	Vertical farming had the highest environmental impact, with electricity use contributing to most of it.
(de Jesus Pereira et al., 2021)	Lettuce	cradle to farm gate	Intercropping of vegetables (lettuce tomatoes and cucumber) and monoculture (Brazil)	1 ha of cultivation and 1 kg of lettuce	Intercropping system had a lower GWP than monoculture, mainly due to less infrastructure, fertilisers, and tractor operations.
(Martin et al., 2023)	Lettuce	cradle to grave	Vertical farming with different electricity mixes (Sweden), greenhouse (Italy from Fusi et al. (2016), Netherlands from Blom et al. (2022), open-field (Sweden, Spain from Casey et al. (2022))	1 kg of packaged edible lettuce available to the consumer	Vertically farmed lettuce had a comparable environmental impact to domestically produced conventional lettuce. Vertically farmed lettuce using only renewable electricity from wind had a lower footprint than all conventional systems studied.
(Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2023)	Lettuce	cradle to farm gate	Open-field with 0 %,50 %,100 % desalinated water for irrigation.	1 kg lettuce	Higher environmental impact for the use of desalinated water, due to high energy requirements. Impact could be mitigated by using renewable energy source.

- 1) How does the environmental impact of an agroecologically-grown salad mix value chain compare with that of conventional and hydroponic value chains for providing leafy greens to the UK during winter?
- 2) What are the environmental hotspots of the agroecological production chain?

2. Materials and methods

This study follows the four stages of the ISO Standard 14040 (ISO, 2006): goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory analysis, life cycle impact assessment, and interpretation. The goal of this study was to understand how the environmental impact of delivering leafy greens to the UK from a Portuguese agroecological system compares with existing leafy greens value chains. The reason for carrying such a study lies in the increasing challenges that leafy greens production chains face to meet the high demand from British consumers of lettuce that are largely imported from outside of the UK, notably those of water scarcity, adverse weather events, and rising energy prices. No previous study has examined the environmental impact of a leafy greens agroecological system, and our study is addressed to academics working in the field of food environmental sustainability, and more broadly to consumers of leafy greens and sector stakeholders wishing to gain a broader knowledge on the complexities of supplying a popular, simple food product. The functional unit assessed was 1 kg of packaged salad delivered to the UK. The salad mixes, although different in composition, are considered to be equivalent for the purpose of the LCA, based on the reasoning that a consumer can choose between different types of leafy greens on the supermarket shelf and would regard the various types of leafy greens as direct substitutes. Therefore, no allocation was necessary at the farm level as the leafy greens mix from the agroecological system were considered as a whole. System boundaries for the various systems were recorded in Fig. 1. Boundaries were from cradle to regional distribution centre gate, as retail, consumption, and waste at consumer house were assumed to be the same across value chains. Table 2 specifies the characteristics of each system studied.

The OpenLCA software v.1.11.0 (GreenDelta, 2022) was used to model the systems, with the use of Ecoinvent v3.8 cut-off database (Wernet et al., 2016). The impact categories were those sixteen recommended by the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) guidelines (European Commission, 2018), under the OpenLCA – “EF 3.0 Method

Table 2
Description of the salad systems studied.

	System type	Country of production	Agricultural yield (ton/year)
<i>Agro_PT</i>	Agroecological greenhouse	Portugal	36.5
<i>Conv_ES</i>	Conventional field	Spain	71.9
<i>Conv_DesalES</i>	Conventional field with 100 % irrigation water being desalinated water	Spain	71.9
<i>Conv_UK^a</i>	Conventional field	UK	42.2
<i>CEA_UK</i>	Hydroponics CEA with the UK electricity mix	UK	1538.5
<i>CEA_WindUK</i>	Hydroponics CEA with the wind, on grid electricity source	UK	1538.5

^a This system is not in function during the winter but is used as a comparison point.

(adapted)” package (the package adapted to suit the OpenLCA software - this adaptation does not affect the dataset itself). The PEF-recommended methods package was used as it contains sixteen standardized impact categories that cover a wide range of environmental issues, therefore largely limiting the risks of missing a key environmental hotspot, as the majority of LCA studies have assessed products across a very limited number of impact categories. In addition, the PEF-recommended methods are aligned with regulatory frameworks, which should facilitate use of results to inform policy and compare with other studies. A modified Null Hypothesis Significance Test (mNHST) was performed (Mendoza Beltran et al., 2018) using a Monte Carlo analysis of 1000 runs for each of the systems studied within the OpenLCA software v.1.11.0 (GreenDelta, 2022). Uncertainty values for each process were determined using the pedigree matrix system from the Ecoinvent data quality system schema (Wernet et al., 2016), so that the different data qualities were taken into account. The hypothesis “the studied production systems delivering one kilogram of packed salad to the UK are associated with different environmental impacts” was tested statistically. The null hypothesis tested assumed that the environmental impacts of the studied salad systems were equal. We applied the Bonferroni correction of the significance level to exclude false positives, as $\alpha_b = 0.05/96 = 0.0005$. The 96 factor represents the sixteen environmental impact categories and six pairs of alternatives. All threshold values were tested with an effect size (δ) of 0.2.

Fig. 1. System boundaries of the systems studied.

The life cycle inventories of all systems studied are recorded in Table 3. Primary data for the agroecological system were collected from Biofontinhas (Projecto, 2022), a farm in the Azores (Portugal), whereas data on the hydroponic CEA and UK field-based system were extracted from Casey et al. (2022). The Spanish conventional field-based and desalination scenarios were modelled using the study by Martin-Gorriz et al. (2020) for the general LCA inventory, the study by Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2020) for the water and Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2023). Seed input per hectare was modelled to be the same as in Conv_UK. For the conventional, agroecological, and desalinated systems, direct and indirect field emissions of nitrous oxide from crop residues were calculated following the eqs. 11.2 and 11.10 of IPCC guidelines (Hergoualc'h et al., 2019). Indirect emissions from nitrate losses to water were calculated according to Reckling et al. (2016), as the IPCC guidelines only cover greenhouse gas emissions. Indirect emissions of CO₂ from lime application were calculated following IPCC guidelines (De Klein et al., 2006). Distinctions were made between dry (Spain) and wet (UK and Azores) climates following the IPCC guidelines (Hergoualc'h et al., 2019), however the type of soil was not taken into account. Phosphorus losses to water due to synthetic and organic fertilisers were calculated based on cropping system loss coefficients of 1 % (Styles et al., 2015). All other background processes were sourced from the Ecoinvent v3.8 cut-off database (Wernet et al., 2016). Water for washing of leafy greens, packaging, and cooling was modelled identically across all systems, as in Maynard et al. (2023).

2.1. Agroecological system

The Agro_PT leafy greens produced are part of a rotation consisting of lettuce (47 % of salad mix), swisschard (*Beta vulgaris* subsp. *Vulgaris*, 11 % of salad mix), golden purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*, 9 % of salad mix), garden orache (*Atriplex hortensis*, 11 % of salad mix), buck's-horn plantain (*Plantago coroponus*, 12 % of salad mix), and ten mustard plants from the Brassica genus (11 % of salad mix), such as tatsoi (*Brassica rapa*, 7 % of salad mix). The crops are grown all year-round, representing 7 cycles yearly. This is possible thanks to the temperate, subtropical climate of the island. The leafy greens are grown on a volcanic soil, where no ploughing nor tilling occurs, with no engines at soil level. Only inputs that were used for the growth of leafy greens were modelled, thus excluding other elements of the agroecological farm, like the agroforestry part. The plants are grown in a greenhouse made of steel and plastics. Basic data for greenhouse material and life span were extracted from Torrellas et al. (2012), namely steel, low density polyethylene, and polycarbonate. One operator works with a fork for 5 min per square meter to prepare the soil. Only 25 % of the seeds sown are purchased, with the remaining having been collected on farm from previous cycles. No fertiliser is applied, apart from farm-owned compost and foliar fertiliser made on site with weeds. Soil replenishment of nutrients going to the leafy greens mainly come from manure application within the compost. Emissions from compost production were calculated following Bishop et al. (2021), adjusting the compost content for leafy greens (5 %), mixed vegetables (10 %), tree trimmings (60 %), and poultry and swine manure (25 %), which represent a NPK content of 7–2.5–5.9 in percentage fresh weight. A compost density of 542.5 kg.m³ was extracted from Khater (2015). Emissions from compost applications were calculated following the IPCC guidelines (Hergoualc'h et al., 2019). Following the approach in Bishop et al. (2021) and Tonini et al. (2018), long-term (100 year) biogenic carbon sequestration from compost production and application was calculated as 11.3 % of the non-degraded carbon content of the compost. The carbon content being 55.5 % of the farm compost dry matter, the dry matter content of the compost being of 27 %, and with 1 kg of compost being applied per m², this represented 0.23 kg.m⁻² long-term biogenic carbon sequestered. In addition, 35 g of calcium carbonate is applied per square meter every five years. Two pesticides, Pirecris and Turex, are applied 25 times a year. However, pesticide emissions were not modelled in this study due

to current limitations in emission modelling and toxicity characterization factors of pesticides. A total of 480 m³ of municipal water is used yearly for the leafy greens, representing water applied through drip irrigation and manual spray, as well as water for washing harvested products. The leafy greens are harvested manually, washed four times, and packaged into 200 g and 500 g nano-perforated plastic bags for individual consumers and restaurants, respectively. The products are then refrigerated. Even though the case study value chain is local (clients pick up the products directly at the farm), this study modelled a hypothetical export to London (United Kingdom) for benchmarking against other value chains. Transport was assumed to take place via refrigerated truck to the harbour of Praia da Vitória (9 km) and ship (2784 km) to London for 3 days and 15 h (SeaRates, 2022). A sensitivity analysis was performed (Agro_PT_sens) to assess how the environmental impact of the agroecological mix would change if the transport would take place via refrigerated truck (9 km) to the harbour of Praia da Vitória, followed by refrigerated ship to Lisbon for 1551 km (SeaRates, 2022), followed by 2021 km by refrigerated lorry through Portugal, Spain, and France (Google, 2023) and 175 km by refrigerated ship (SeaRates, 2022). This scenario, although much longer than the former scenario, could happen if supply chains are not scaled sufficiently to support regular sea transportation from the Azores to the UK. No empty return of any transport vehicle was modelled for any of the systems in this whole study, as it was assumed that the vehicles would be used to transport other goods. Based on WWF-UK (2021) and assuming that product losses during transport are proportionate to transport distance, a loss of leafy greens during the transport phase was modelled as follows: the 6.4 % post-harvest loss reported by WWF-UK (2021) was attributed to the lettuce grown in Spain, as it is the current dominant value chain supplying the UK. As Spanish lettuce (Conv_ES and Conv_ES_Desal) travels for 2096 km and the leafy greens mix scenario (Agro_PT) travels for 1821 km, and assuming that loss is linear, a cross-product calculation gives a post-harvest loss of 8.6 % for this value chain. For the sensitivity analysis on the Azores transport that travels for 3756 km (Agro_PT_sens), the same approach provides a post-harvest loss of 11.5 %. A sensitivity analysis was performed with the amount of loss quantities during the transport stage doubled. Losses during transport for all value chains were recorded in Table A1 of the Appendix for both the baseline and sensitivity analysis.

2.2. Conventional field-based system

The Conv_UK system represented the average of three farms in the UK, while the Conv_ES system represented systems from the South-East region of Spain, where crops are grown intensively for exportation. As mentioned in Casey et al. (2022), cultivation data for the British system were extracted from Milà i Canals et al. (2008). For the Spanish data, the N fertiliser mix was specified in Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2020), resulting in the source of nitrogen from synthetic origin being from nitrate (72 %) and ammonium nitrate (28 %). The conventional field-based systems were characterised by the transplantation of young lettuce plugs from a nursery in a greenhouse to the field. Plugs of 18 g each containing 80 % peat were transported for 40 km between the nursery and the farm. Transport from Murcia to London consisted of 1900 km by refrigerated lorry (Google, 2023) and 175 km by refrigerated ship (SeaRates, 2022) for Conv_ES, and 202 km by refrigerated lorry for Conv_UK (Casey et al., 2022). As mentioned above, a post-harvest loss factor for transport of 6.4 % was modelled.

2.3. Conventional field-based system with desalinated water

The Conv_DesalES scenario was modelled adjusting the Conv_ES scenario for the energy, irrigation, and fertiliser requirements based on Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2023). Irrigation requirements decrease when using desalinated water, as the total irrigation requirement was 8 % lower for the use of 100 % desalinated water when compared to the baseline scenario in Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2023), and therefore the

Table 3

Life cycle inventories of the salad systems studied for 1 kg of salad packaged at the distribution centre in the UK.

Stage	Input / output / process	Units	Hydroponics CEA Wind on grid		Hydroponics CEA		Field- Spain		Field- Spain Desalination		Field- Great Britain		Agroecological BIOFO	
			Lettuce		Lettuce		Lettuce		Lettuce		Lettuce		Salad mix	
			In	Out	In	Out	In	Out	In	Out	In	Out	In	Out
Infrastructure construction	Steel structure	kg	0.029 ^{b1}		0.029 ^{b1}									0.15 ^d
	Low density polyethylene	kg												0.04 ^d
	Polycarbonate	kg												0.003 ^d
Agricultural stage	Aluminium towers	kg	0.035 ^{b1}		0.035 ^{b1}									
	Pumps(s)	units	3.70E-06 ^{b1}		3.70E-06 ^{b1}									
	LED lights	units	0.081 ^{b1}		0.081 ^{b1}									
	Peat (growing media)	kg	0.008 ^{b1}		0.008 ^{b1}		0.038 ^{b2}		0.038 ^{b2}		0.028 ^{b1}			
	Coco fibre (growing media)	kg	0.008 ^{b1}		0.008 ^{b1}									
	Polystyrene tray	kg					0.001 ^{b2}		0.001 ^{b2}		0.001 ^{b1}			
	Fertiliser - N (total)	kg	0.002 ^{b1}		0.002 ^{b1}		0.010 ^{b2}		0.011 ^{b2}		0.003 ^{b1}			0.021 ^a
	of which N from manure	kg					0.002 ^{b2}		0.002 ^{b2}					
	of which N from inorganic	kg	0.002 ^{b1}		0.002 ^{b1}		0.009 ^{b2}		0.009 ^{b2}					0.021 ^a
	of which N from compost	kg												0.068 ^c
	Long-term carbon sequestration from compost	kg CO ₂												
	Fertiliser - P (from manure, inorganic, and/or compost)	kg	0.001 ^{b1}		0.001 ^{b1}		0.002 ^{b2}		0.002 ^{b2}		0.001 ^{b1}			0.008 ^a
	Fertiliser - K (from manure, inorganic, and/or compost)	kg	0.002 ^{b1}		0.002 ^{b1}		0.009 ^{b2}		0.008 ^{b2}		0.002 ^{b1}			0.017 ^a
	Calcium	kg	0.002 ^{b1}		0.002 ^{b1}				0.001 ^{b2}					
	Magnesium sulphate	kg	0.002 ^{b1}		0.002 ^{b1}				0.001 ^{b2}					
	Iron(III) sulfate, without water, in 12.5 % iron solution state	kg	0.0004 ^{b1}		0.0004 ^{b1}									
	Lime	kg									0.012 ^{b1}			2.0E-11 ^a
	Electricity, from country grid	kWh			15 ^{b1}					0.698 ^{b2}		0.031 ^{b1}		
	Electricity, wind, <1 MW turbine, onshore, renewable	kWh	15 ^{b1}				0.011 ^{b2}							
	Diesel	kg					0.013 ^{b2}		0.013 ^{b2}		0.017 ^{b1}			
Pesticides	kg					3.2E-04 ^{b2}		3.2E-04 ^{b2}		2.0E-04 ^{b1}			1.1E-04 ^a	
CO ₂	kg	0.081 ^{b1}		0.081 ^{b1}										
Water (irrigation)	L	1.6 ^{b1}		1.6 ^{b1}		198.0 ^{b2}		182.157 ^{b2}		37.228 ^{b1}			21.831 ^a	
Seeds purchased	kg	1.21E-06 ^{b1}		1.21E-06 ^{b1}		0.103 ^{b2}		0.103 ^{b2}		0.098 ^{b1}			0.0002 ^a	
Land	ha.	6.50E-07 ^{b1}		6.50E-07 ^{b1}		4.0E-05 ^{b2}		4.0E-05 ^{b2}		2.4E-05 ^{b1}			2.9E-05 ^a	
	year ⁻¹													
	Purchased seeds transport (truck >32 t, EURO 4)	kg.km	0.0002 ^{b1}		0.0002 ^{b1}		13.4 ^c		13.4 ^c		12.7 ^c			0.03 ^c
	Purchased seeds transport (train)	kg.km	0.0003 ^{b1}		0.0003 ^{b1}		24.8 ^c		24.8 ^c		23.4 ^c			0.1 ^c
	Purchased seeds transport (ship)	kg.km	0.0003 ^{b1}		0.0003 ^{b1}		28.0 ^c		28.0 ^c		26.5 ^c			0.1 ^c
Washing and sorting of leafy greens	Water	kg	0.074 ^a		0.074 ^a		0.079 ^a		0.079 ^a		0.074 ^a			0.080 ^a
	Waste leafy greens to compost	kg												0.753 ^a
	Wastewater	kg		0.074 ^a		0.074 ^a		0.079 ^a		0.079 ^a		0.074 ^a		0.080 ^a
Packaging	Nano-perforated bag (500 g content), 2 items	kg	0.01 ^a		0.01 ^a		0.011 ^a		0.011 ^a		0.010 ^a			0.011 ^a
	Packaging transport (truck >32 t, EURO 4)	kg.km	2.3 ^c		2.3 ^c		2.4 ^c		2.4 ^c		2.3 ^c			2.5 ^c
	Packaging transport (train)	kg.km	2.8 ^c		2.8 ^c		3.0 ^c		3.0 ^c		2.8 ^c			3.04 ^c
	Packaging transport (ship)	kg.km	3.6 ^c		3.6 ^c		3.8 ^c		3.8 ^c		3.6 ^c			3.91 ^c
Refrigeration	Electricity (refrigeration)	kWh	0.007 ^c		0.007 ^c		0.007 ^c		0.007 ^c		0.007 ^c			0.008 ^c
	1 kg delivered bag of lettuce/salad mix	Units		1		1		1		1		1		1
Delivery	Transport, lorry with refrigeration machine	kg.km					2042 ^c		2042 ^c		203 ^c			10 ^c
	Transport, container ship with reefer, cooling	kg.km					188 ^c		188 ^c					3054 ^c

^a Primary data.

^{b1} Secondary data from Casey et al. (2022).

^{b2} Secondary data from Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2023).

^c Calculated.

^d Secondary data from Torrellas et al. (2012).

irrigation water was adjusted in this scenario following that decrease. Moreover, the specific energy consumption of 3.49 kWh/m³ to convert seawater to desalinated water was also modelled following Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2023). Because desalinated water is low in essential nutrients for crop growth, for example calcium, magnesium, and sulphate, fertiliser requirements differ from when using conventional water sources (Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2023). To calculate this variability, data were extracted from Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2020) and percentage differences recorded between the reference and 100 % use of desalinated water in that study were applied to this case study. Consequently, N fertiliser increased by 6 % and K fertiliser decreased by 3 % when going from *Conv_ES* to *Conv_DesalES*, and CaO and MgO inputs were of 0.0012 kg and 0.0014 kg per kg lettuce harvested in *Conv_DesalES*. The N fertiliser mix was also specified in Martínez-Alvarez et al. (2020), resulting in the source of nitrogen from synthetic origin being from nitrate (71 %) and ammonium nitrate (29 %). The microelement complex was not modelled as the quantities of each microelement was not specified in the original study (Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2020).

2.4. Hydroponics controlled environment systems

The *CEA_UK* and *CEA_WindUK* data were extracted from Casey et al. (2022), which collected primary commercial data from a British company using vertical aluminium towers in steel shipping containers of 28 m². As per definition, the environment is completely controlled, using LED lights, fertilisers, pH buffers, and a heating, ventilation and air conditioning system that regulate the temperature, light, nutrient concentration, and humidity levels. One of the main advantages of the CEA system is that it can be installed in virtually any location, and it was therefore assumed to be at the point of collection in London as in Casey et al. (2022), thus requiring no transport. Two CEA systems were modelled, *CEA_UK* that uses the present UK electricity grid, which consists of mainly natural gas and nuclear sources, and *CEA_WindUK* that uses electricity fully generated by renewable wind energy with grid connection (Wernet et al., 2016). This second scenario was selected over the other CEA scenarios in Casey et al. (2022), as it was the CEA scenario with the lowest environmental footprint identified in the previous study. This additional scenario was included to show the potential impact with a shift to renewable energy sources, as part of the UK Net Zero strategy (Department for Business, 2021).

A few data points differed from the study by Casey et al. (2022). Magnesium and Sulphur were modelled as being provided in the form of magnesium sulphate, as in Chen et al. (2020). Because magnesium was the limiting element, the amount of magnesium sulphate modelled was the one required for magnesium, so sulphur was supplied in a bigger quantity than needed. Iron was brought in the form of iron (III) sulphate, without water, in 12.5 % iron solution state. As mentioned above, no post-harvest loss was modelled.

2.5. Upscaling production in the Azores

In 2021, the United Kingdom imported 178,256 t of lettuce and chicory from Spain (FAO, 2023), which represents the majority of its imports of lettuce (Fig. 2). This study aimed to investigate whether, in theory, the Azores could replace Spanish exports to the United Kingdom, as the islands possess a more suitable climate to grow salad leaves than the South of Spain, which increasingly suffers from water scarcity.

With a surface of 2322 km² and a usable agricultural area (UAA) of 120,400 ha, agricultural activity – in particular livestock farming and fishing – is one of the main economic revenue of the Azores (Massot, 2015). Most of the agricultural land is dedicated to livestock farming, with permanent grasslands/pastures and arable land mainly producing green maize for livestock feed representing 88 % and 10 % of the UAA, respectively (Massot, 2015). In 2020, 10 % of the horticultural land area in the Azores was used to grow lettuce, representing 109.58 ha (SREA, 2020). Using the yields of salad production from the agroecological

Fig. 2. Total amount of lettuce and chicory imported to the UK in 2021 by country, in kilotonnes (data from FAO (2023)).

system in the Azores, this research investigated how much land would be required to produce the equivalent of the Spanish imported lettuce and chicory to the United Kingdom.

3. Results

3.1. General results

The general results of the LCA are reported in Table 4. The *Agro_PT* system was associated with burdens that were significantly lower than those of *Conv_ES*, *Conv_DesalES*, *CEA_UK*, and *CEA_WindUK* across 11, 11, 13, and 7 out of the 16 impact categories, respectively. One kilogram of salad mix from the *Agro_PT* system had a climate change burden that was between 6 % (*CEA_WindUK*) and 90 % (*CEA_UK*) lower than the presented winter alternatives. It also had a fossils resource use that was between 11 % (*CEA_WindUK*) and 95 % (*CEA_UK*) lower than the same alternatives. On the other hand, the *Conv_UK* scenario was associated with burdens that were significantly lower than *Agro_PT* across 9 categories, and with burdens that were statistically significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than *Agro_PT* across 2 categories. Indeed, *Agro_PT* had a 24 % lower acidification and 67 % lower land use than *Conv_UK*. *Conv_UK* had a climate change burden that was 31 % lower than that of *Agro_PT*.

Marine eutrophication was the category across which all systems had a statistically significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) environmental burden than *Agro_PT*, ranging from a 38 % smaller impact (*CEA_UK*) to a 91 % smaller impact (*CEA_WindUK*). The particulate matter burden of *Agro_PT* was also statistically significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than that of all the other systems. Despite the relatively large differences in water scarcity results, these were not statistically significant, due to a high uncertainty around the values.

In order to identify which impact categories were the most concerning in term of impact, normalised results of the systems studied in global person year equivalents using the factors provided by the EF Method 3.0 (adapted) (GreenDelta, 2022) were recorded in Fig. 3, excluding the toxicity-related categories, following the PEF guidelines (European Commission, 2018), due to their high associated uncertainty. Results from the sensitivity analysis *Agro_PT_sens* were also included in that figure. Ionising radiation, resource use, fossils, and minerals and metals were the three impact categories with the highest normalised environmental burdens for the *CEA_UK* scenario, with 1 kg of delivered lettuce emitting >0.0009 of an average person's impact across these categories in a year. The only other salad system which had an impact superior to that number was the *Conv_ES* scenario in the water scarcity category. In *Agro_PT*, the highest burdens were in marine eutrophication and particulate matter. The *CEA_WindUK* scenario had the smallest land use footprint when compared with the other systems (between 59 % and 91 % reduction, depending on the system compared), showing potential

Table 4

General LCA results of the salad systems studied for 1 kg of delivered salad bag to the UK. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) is recorded in red and green, indicating environmental burdens that were higher or lower than those of the agroecological system, respectively. White indicates no statistical significance.

Name	Unit	Conv_UK	Conv_ES	Conv_DesalES	CEA_UK	CEA_WindUK	Agro_PT
Acidification	mol H ⁺ eq	0.007	0.010	0.011	0.029	0.006	0.005
Climate change (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	0.37	0.63	0.73	5.22	0.57	0.54
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	14.0	31.4	40.9	87.8	20.3	9.2
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0011	0.0002	0.0002
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	0.0019	0.0026	0.0027	0.0041	0.0006	0.0066
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	0.022	0.030	0.032	0.022	0.006	0.019
Human toxicity, carcinogenic	CTUh	2.8E-10	4.4E-10	5.1E-10	2.8E-09	1.6E-09	1.6E-09
Human toxicity, non-carcinogenic	CTUh	8.7E-09	1.4E-08	1.5E-08	7.0E-08	1.7E-08	8.7E-09
Ionising radiation (human health)	kBq U-235 eq	0.03	0.06	0.10	4.37	0.03	0.02
Land use	Points	34.9	51.1	35.9	54.1	4.6	11.4
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	3.8E-08	9.2E-08	1.0E-07	3.5E-07	2.6E-08	2.8E-08
Particulate matter	disease incidence	3.5E-08	6.4E-08	6.7E-08	1.1E-07	3.6E-08	1.4E-07
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	0.002	0.004	0.004	0.011	0.002	0.003
	MJ, net calorific						
Resource use, fossils	value	4.5	9.0	10.8	130.2	6.7	6.0
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	3.0E-06	5.8E-06	7.5E-06	6.1E-05	1.2E-05	3.4E-06
Water use (user deprivation potential)	m ³ world eq. deprived	1.76	13.38	0.62	0.52	0.28	1.18

to spare land. However, as shown in this study with the normalisation of the results, land use is not one of the most concerning categories.

3.2. Process contributions

Process contributions of the systems representing potential future options to substitute the current Spanish lettuce delivery to the UK during the winter months (*Conv_DesalES*, *CEA_WindUK*, *Agro_PT*) were recorded in Fig. 4.

3.2.1. Conventional desalinated system in Spain

The agricultural stage of *Conv_DesalES* was responsible for most of the environmental impact across most of the categories, contributing to 77 %, 59 %, 90 %, 54 %, 86 %, and 93 % of total acidification, climate change, land use, fossil resource use, minerals and metals use, and water scarcity burdens, respectively. Seed production was responsible for 25 % of the climate change burden within the agricultural stage, while electricity caused 17 % of it, and another 17 % were from diesel burned in agricultural machinery, and 7 % from irrigation. In the fossil fuels resource use category, seed production was responsible for 14 % of the total impact in the agricultural stage, electricity caused 29 % of it, 15 % were from diesel burned in agricultural machinery, 11 % from irrigation, and 7 % from peat. In the minerals and metals use category, seed production was responsible for 14 % of the total impact in the agricultural stage, electricity caused 12 % of it, 12 % were from diesel burned in agricultural machinery, 27 % from irrigation, 11 % from calcium nitrate and 10 % from potassium sulphate. Land use in the agricultural stage

was mostly due to seed production (68 %). Lastly, seed production contributed to 76 % of the total water use burden in the agricultural stage.

Distribution was a secondary hotspot for *Conv_DesalES*, contributing to 17 %, 36 %, 36 %, and 48 % of the total acidification, climate change, fossil fuels use, and photochemical ozone formation impact categories, respectively. These were due to the emission of fossil CO₂ in the climate change category, nitrogen oxides in the acidification and photochemical ozone formation categories, and the ground extraction of crude oil in the fossil fuels resource use category.

3.2.2. Hydroponics system with wind electricity on grid in the UK

In *CEA_WindUK*, the major contributors were the infrastructure and agriculture stages. Infrastructure was responsible for 56 %, 59 %, 64 %, 53 %, and 44 % of the total acidification, climate change, freshwater eutrophication, fossil resource use, and minerals and metals use, respectively. These impacts were due to the use of aluminium, followed by light emitting diodes, and finally steel. For example, the use of aluminium was responsible for 43 % of the acidification burden of the infrastructure, while the use of light emitting diodes caused 41 % of it, and the remaining 16 % were due to the use of steel. In the climate change category, 59 %, 22 % and 19 % of the burdens were due to aluminium, light emitting diodes, and steel, respectively.

Besides this, the agricultural stage of *CEA_WindUK* contributed to 33 %, 34 %, 32 %, 54 %, and 53 % of total acidification, climate change, fossil resource use, minerals and metals use, and water scarcity, respectively. For the first four categories mentioned, the major

Fig. 3. Normalised LCA results of the salad systems studied for 1 kg of delivered salad bag to the UK, in person per year equivalents.

contributor was electricity production from wind, followed by the use of liquid carbon dioxide, and finally N and P inorganic fertilisers. For example, electricity production from wind was responsible for 58 % of the total acidification burden of the agricultural stage, and liquid carbon dioxide represented an additional 25 % of it. The use of inorganic N and P fertilisers was associated with 6 % and 5 % of the acidification burden of the agricultural stage. In the climate change category, the electricity production from wind caused 47 % of the burdens in the agricultural stage, followed by 39 % from liquid carbon dioxide, and 5 % and 4 % from the inorganic N and P fertilisers. In the water use category of the agricultural stage, 45 % of the burden was due to the market for tap water, followed by 33 % due to electricity production from wind.

3.2.3. Agroecological system in Portugal

As in *CEA_WindUK*, the major contributors in *Agro_PT* were the infrastructure and agriculture stages. The greenhouse infrastructure was responsible for 47 %, 51 %, 68 %, 68 %, and 79 % of the total acidification, climate change, freshwater eutrophication, fossil resource use, and minerals and metals use, respectively. The agricultural stage was also responsible for 29 %, 89 %, and 87 % of total climate change, marine eutrophication, and water scarcity of *Agro_PT*, respectively. Dinitrogen monoxide emitted to the air from the application of compost and steel production for the greenhouse were the main contributors to the climate change burdens. The emission of nitrate to the water from compost application was responsible for 80 % of the marine eutrophication burden. In the particulate matter category, the high emission of ammonia to the air from compost application was responsible for most of the impact. The high environmental burdens of this system in the

agricultural phase are mainly because much higher amounts of N were applied on field when compared to the other systems, leading to high emissions of compounds such as nitrate, dinitrogen monoxide, etc. For example, to obtain 1 kg of leafy greens in the UK from *Agro_PT*, around twice the amount of N applied in *Conv_ES* was used.

It is worth noting that the distribution phase of *Conv_ES* has a higher environmental impact across all categories than *Agro_PT*, despite the greater transport distance of the *Agro_PT* salad mix. Every km of lorry with reefer, cooling, is associated with a climate change burden that is 5 times higher than a km of freight shipping with reefer, cooling, mainly due to a higher carbon dioxide emission to the air.

3.2.4. Sensitivity analysis: agroecological system in Portugal with modified transport route

We also investigated the environmental burden associated with alternative distribution pathways where instead of direct shipping to the UK, the leafy greens are transported through mainland Portugal, Spain, and France by refrigerated truck before being loaded on another refrigerated ship to cross the UK. Environmental burdens of the extended transport pathway (*Agro_PT_sens*) were found to be between 4 % and 210 % larger than direct shipping to UK (*Agro_PT*), with a 51 % larger climate change burden and 69 % larger fossil fuels use (Fig. 3).

3.2.5. Sensitivity analysis: post-harvest supply chain loss

Following a doubling of lettuce loss during transport compared with default estimates described in the Methodology, the results of the sensitivity analysis as well as statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) of differences between environmental burdens for leafy greens from the

Fig. 4. Process contributions for Conv_DesalES (A), CEA_WindUK (B), and Agro_PT (C).

Agro_PT system versus other value chains were recorded in Table A2 of the Appendix. Climate change burdens went from 0.54 kg CO₂ equivalents for *Agro_PT* in the baseline scenario to 0.58 kg CO₂ equivalents, resulting in no statistical significance between the climate change burdens of *CEA_WindUK* and *Agro_PT*. Besides this, the results of the sensitivity analysis differed only in the ozone depletion category, where leafy green from *Agro_PT* had a statistically significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) environmental footprint than lettuce from three, rather than four, other value chains, and in photochemical ozone formation category, where leafy greens from *Agro_PT* had a statistically significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) environmental footprint than two, rather than three, value chains.

On the other hand, when following a doubling of lettuce loss during transport compared with default estimates described in the Methodology, and comparing differences between environmental burdens for leafy greens from the *Agro_PT_sens* system (Table A3 of the Appendix), climate change burdens associated with *Agro_PT_sens* were statistically significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than those of *Conv_UK*, *Conv_ES*, *CEA_WindUK*, not statistically significantly different ($p < 0.05$) than those of *Conv_DesalES*, and still statistically significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than those of *CEA_UK*. This shows that a higher post-harvest loss during transport associated with a longer, non-optimised transport route can reverse the environmental advantages of such a value chain.

4. Discussion

This case study is the first to address the comparative environmental benefits and trade-offs of growing underutilised leafy greens as a salad crop incorporating an agroecological approach, compared to a variety of lettuce production systems; agroecological greenhouse production in Portugal, conventional field production in Spain, conventional field production in Spain with 100 % irrigation water being desalinated water, conventional field production in the UK, hydroponics CEA production in the UK with the UK electricity mix, and hydroponics CEA production in the UK with the wind, on grid electricity source. This case study also considers the possibility of substituting Spanish lettuce imports to the UK with leafy greens from the Azores. Despite a number of comparative environmental benefits in agroecological production of leafy greens, such as a 13–90 % smaller climate change burden and 18–96 % smaller fossils resource use burden compared with the other value chains, only where direct shipping of leafy greens to the UK is considered is the Azores system plausible.

Overall, the delivery of agroecological salad mix to the UK was associated with an environmental impact that was statistically significantly lower than the other studied winter systems across 7 to 13 out of the 16 categories assessed. These results raise the possibility of providing a completely different source of salad leaves from the current market in a potentially less environmentally harmful way, while increasing diversity on land.

Statistically significant environmental trade-offs associated with the agroecological salad mix were also captured in this LCA. The system was associated with an environmental impact that was statistically significantly higher than the winter studied systems across 2 impact categories: marine eutrophication and particulate matter. This was due to the application of large amounts of N-rich compost during the agricultural stage, leading to high emissions of compounds such as nitrate, dinitrogen monoxide, etc. The input of N in this system may be too large, and other studies should therefore investigate the optimal amount of N input in such a system. Moreover, accurate measurements of N leaching should be performed.

Additionally, the greenhouse infrastructure was responsible for a major portion of the burdens across most impact categories. This hotspot had previously been identified in other LCA studies of lettuce production (Anton et al., 2005; Romero-Gómez et al., 2014). These authors concluded that efforts on changing the greenhouse structure and using recycled materials would considerably reduce the environmental impact of the salad leaves.

Moreover, the agroecological system was characterised by a lower yield than the conventional system in the UK and the Hydroponics system in the UK. As in Romero-Gómez et al. (2014), where escarole and lettuce production systems were investigated and a lower commercial yield for escarole resulted in a higher impact than if yields were optimised, the underutilised leafy greens of our study were characterised by lower yields when compared to lettuce. Lower inputs linked to lower yields are common features of agroecological systems, which can address serious limitations attributed to conventional food production: climate change, pollution, loss of farming jobs, and declining food quality (Hatt et al., 2016). The question arises as to whether and how a viable economy and food security can be maintained while producing less food per unit area of land. This question is beyond the scope of LCA, which only provides quantification of environmental intensity of production (to infer production efficiency). Such analyses ignore holistic sustainable food system considerations including food (security) sufficiency, resilience, fairer distribution, and social wellbeing. These contrasting views were described by Garnett (2014), where LCA often belongs to the efficiency-oriented perspective, and contrasts with the demand restraint and food system transformation perspectives that criticise the status quo of excessive consumption.

Additionally, more labour hours may be required, as the agroecological system in the Azores has seven cycles yearly for its leafy greens and no machinery is used, as mentioned earlier. On one hand, this contributes to generating employment, but on the other hand, it is not as economically efficient as using agricultural machinery. This concept has been discussed elsewhere, stating that increasing labour or yield efficiency in agriculture often comes at the expense of a decrease of ecosystem services, biodiversity loss, etc. (Wezel et al., 2020), and that increased crop diversity is associated with higher agricultural employment rates (Garibaldi and Pérez-Méndez, 2019). Another limitation of this study is that the LCA methodology fails to capture burdens related to the littering and microplastic pollution risk of plastic-film packaging (Pellengahr et al., 2023), which could be reduced through alternative or reduced packaging that local CEA supply chains could potentially offer. As it is estimated that 14 % of microplastics found in the environment come from littering (Ryberg et al., 2019) and that the end-of-life of nearly 80 % of all plastics produced are not properly dealt with, eventually accumulating in the environment or landfills (Geyer et al., 2017) it is crucial to minimise plastic packaging usage, improve its waste collection and recycling, and set stricter regulations for its production and consumption (Prata et al., 2019). Although plastic packaging greatly improves shelf life if well designed, its release to the environment has become a global problem, affecting wildlife, human health, and the global environment (Li et al., 2021). These additional, non-LCA factors need to be assessed to fully understand the sustainability and resilience factors of all systems.

The fact that the distribution phase of the conventional systems in

Spain was associated with a higher environmental burden than the distribution phase of the agroecological system may be counter-intuitive, as the agroecological Biofontinhas farm is located on an island in the middle of the Atlantic Ocean while Spain seems better connected to the UK. Currently, the transport of lettuce from Spain is mainly done by truck (92 % of the total distance). A study from Hospido et al. (2009) also found that refrigerated transport to the UK was an important contributor to the global warming potential associated with Spanish lettuce (42.5 % of total emissions). This study agrees with the fact that refrigerated transport can affect the overall environmental impact of salad value chains, with a different route for the agroecological mix resulting in a 47 % increase of the climate change impact of the product, giving it a higher impact than all value chains but *CEA_UK*. Where long distance transport of food is required, value chains may therefore need to be at larger (minimum viable) scale, or cooperation with other producers with similar markets should be established, to allow more efficient transport routes. Additionally, while the sensitivity analysis where loss of leafy greens during the transport stage was doubled showed little difference with the baseline model of *Agro_PT*, combining the doubling of post-harvest loss from transport with the longer route of *Agro_PT_sens* resulted in the underutilised leafy greens value chain having a higher climate change burden than *Conv_UK*, *Conv_ES*, and *CEA_WindUK*. This indicates that careful design of transport route and prevention of product loss during transport are essential to preserve any comparative carbon emission benefits.

Due to the uniqueness of the agroecological farm in the Azores, it was not possible to assess several farms to ensure representativity of this system. Consequently, no inter-farm variability was represented. Moreover, temporal variability was not considered. The environmental impact of lettuce production was calculated for a conventional system in the UK; however, it should be noted that the time of the year data were extracted from was not specified. The supply of UK-grown salad varies greatly depending on the season, with the country importing mostly lettuce from the EU in autumn and winter, while in Summer domestic production replaces most of the imports (Department for Environment, 2021). This lack of self-sufficiency throughout the year makes the UK prone to various factors. In March 2023, supermarkets in the UK were facing great shortages on lettuce due to Brexit, abnormal climatic conditions, and labour shortages and high energy costs for UK production, according to the Financial Times (Evans et al., 2023). Therefore, although *Conv_UK* seems to be one of the systems with the less environmental harm, it should not be considered as a year-long solution, giving the other systems more relevance in a wider context. Another critical question that rises already raised by Hospido et al. (2009) is whether the UK needs to continue consuming lettuce during the winter months. A switch in dietary habits, however, is challenging and consumers may not be willing to make the effort (Duram and Oberholtzer, 2010). Consuming a different type of salad, as proposed in this study with the agroecological salad mix may also be challenging, and conducting further research on consumer acceptance in the UK would be necessary if such a supply chain would be established.

It should be noted that the water consumption in *Conv_ES* seemed particularly high, with 198 L of irrigation water used to obtain 1 kg of packaged lettuce (Table 3). Previous LCA studies of lettuce cultivation in Spain have recorded way less water consumption per kg output of lettuce grown in an open field system, from 30 L of irrigation water per kg of lettuce delivered (Romero-Gómez et al., 2014) to a maximum of slightly >100 L (Hospido et al., 2009). However, these systems were assessed at around 10 years before the study used in this paper, and water scarcity as well as average temperatures were not as high as nowadays (AEMET, 2015).

Besides the environmental costs, the economic costs and benefits are likely to differ between the systems, for example the use of 100 % of desalinated water incurs a cost per cubic meter of water that is 2.75 times higher than when using the conventional water sources (Martínez-Alvarez et al., 2020). This highlights the need for more complete

comparisons between leafy greens value chains. Similarly, while the provision of 1 kg of salad mix from the *Agro_PT* system did not show the lowest environmental burdens across all categories when compared to the other systems, it should be noted that other key environmental attributes that are not captured by LCA would be better met by this system, such as non-provisioning ecosystem services and resilience. As mentioned previously, it is therefore urgent to develop other tools that can complement the LCA approach in a parallel assessment format.

This study also highlighted the fact that environmental burdens can vary significantly within a given production system. For example, a reduction of climate change impact of 89 % and fossil fuels resources reduction of 94 % was achieved when going from *CEA_UK* to *CEA_WindUK*. These results are in line with those of the original study on hydroponically-grown lettuce by Casey et al. (2022), who found a 95 % and 98 % reduction of climate change and fossil fuels resources for the same compared systems. Similarly, a variability of 14 % and 22 % were observed between the burdens of *Conv_ES* and *Conv_Desal_ES* across the climate change and freshwater eutrophication categories, respectively.

As the Spanish agricultural sector is projected to increasingly suffer from adverse climatic conditions due to climate change, adaptation is clearly required (Jiménez-Donaire et al., 2020; Moreno et al., 2005). Even though small islands such as the Azores cannot fully displace production in large countries such as Spain, this study suggests that there is the potential from a climatic and land capacity perspective for developing a market for underutilised leafy greens from countries that do not suffer from extreme heat and drought, such as Spain (Jiménez-Donaire et al., 2020). With one hectare of the *Agro_PT* producing 36.5 t of salad a year, 4884 ha a year would be necessary to supply the 178,256 t of salad leaves to the United Kingdom that currently come from Spain. In 2020, 109.6 ha were used to grow lettuce in the Azores, representing 10 % of the horticultural land area and 0.1 % of the UAA of the islands. Replacing the Spanish exports of salad leaves would therefore result in the use of 4.5 % of the UAA of the Azores. This represents a considerable increase in land area allocated to salad leaves production, however it is feasible, since at present 98 % of the UAA of the Azores is dedicated to the livestock sector, i.e. 117,992 ha, and meat and dairy consumption need to decrease to align with the healthy planetary diet from the EAT Lancet (Willett et al., 2019). Nevertheless, this study does not claim that the Azores should fulfil by itself the UK demand for leafy greens in winter, and socio-economic aspects should be considered. If one accepts that consumer choice should continue throughout the year, a combination of countries resilient to temperature and water supply challenges could meet the UK demand for leafy greens. Once again, if consumers knew the environmental impacts associated with winter supplies, some of them may adopt a more seasonal and local approach to their diet, provided that such products are made accessible to them. Educating consumers on other local leafy greens – such as kale (*Brassica oleracea*), winter purslane (*Claytonia perfoliata*), or Swiss chard (*Beta vulgaris*) – that grow during the winter in the UK, and increasing their visibility in shops could also be beneficial.

Scaling up (in size) or out (in number) of small-scale agro-ecological farms to supply leafy greens to the UK could incur environmental burdens such as land use change from grassland to cropland, and/or realise environmental efficiencies through economies of scale. Therefore, a prospective consequential LCA of large-scale lettuce supply substitution would be required to understand possible indirect effects, which may be combined with scenarios of other food system sustainability transformations (Springmann et al., 2018), such as declining consumption of meat and dairy which could spare pasture land in the Azores (and elsewhere). Finally, there are considerable logistical and marketing challenges associated with large scale shifts in supply chains. Developing new supply chains and marketing channels would require considerable planning. New freight routes to the UK (or nearby in northern Europe) would require a minimum year-round demand to be established, which may require coordinated marketing of across agri-food (or indeed other) exports to particular regions (Morgan et al.,

2022). Purchasing retailers would need to be convinced on the reliability of supply chains, and a marketing campaign may be needed to educate consumers about the provenance, safety and sustainability of crops produced in a lesser-known source of origin – overcoming (mis-)perceptions and over-simplified “sustainability” metrics such as “food miles”. Indeed, public perception of food miles is complicated in that different modes of transport have different climate change burdens per km, the worst being air transport, and that transport share on the total environmental impact of a product depends on the nature of the product. For example, Frankowska et al. (2019) found that vegetables air-freighted to the UK are associated with a climate change burden that is significantly larger than locally-grown vegetables. Listing transport costs per food product is therefore dependent upon the actual pathway, which may differ considerably, as shown in our study. To take account of this, supermarkets could list the proportion of global warming potential of food products in terms of production and transport in their shelving information to allow consumer choice on total climate change impacts. These barriers are surmountable but would require a concerted effort coordinated with high-level (government or agri-food umbrella organisation) support – which is the perpetual challenge for small-scale producers amongst globalised supply chains.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated the environmental impact of an agroecologically-produced salad mix in the Azores and compared the environmental impact of a theoretical supply chain of such a salad mix delivered to London during the winter months with that of a wide range of lettuce supply chains, from conventional, open-field grown supply chains in Spain, to a high technology hydroponics supply chain in the UK. Besides the provision of leafy greens with a comparatively higher diversification of foods in one's diet, the agroecological supply chain was associated with an environmental impact that was statistically significantly lower across seven impact categories when compared to all other winter supply chains, such as across the climate change and fossils resource use categories. It was however associated with statistically significantly higher burdens across the marine eutrophication category. Efforts to reduce the overall impact could focus on infrastructure and the amounts of compost applied on field, which are the two main hotspots. The agroecological supply chain was however associated with overall higher environmental burdens than the field-grown lettuce supply chain in the UK outside of winter, highlighting the question of whether such a commodity needs to be consumed out of season in the country. We suggest that future policies focus on making information readily available to consumers through supermarkets, for example using shelving information on environmental costs of both food production and transportation associated with products that go beyond a simple climate change burden. From an environmental perspective only, this study suggests that policies should be developed that favour local, seasonal products over imported ones, and this could be achieved via incentives for producing and marketing such foods. Generally, increasing road and air-transport costs through e.g. fuel, carbon and road use levies to promote more sustainable transport systems could also favour shorter (more local) supply chains. A different transport route through mainland Europe would also potentially give the agroecological salad mix higher environmental burdens than most of the other systems, highlighting that inefficient distribution of fresh foods may undermine comparative environmental efficiency of a given system. This study also investigated whether the Azores would have the arable land capacity to replace Spain as an exporter of salad leaves to the UK and found that although a significant increase in land dedicated to horticulture would need to be achieved, a total of 4.5 % of the usable agricultural area of the islands would be needed. A prospective, consequential LCA is needed to fully understand the indirect effects of such a shift, in the context of wider transformation of land and food systems towards genuine sustainability and resilience at scale. Finally, because of the limitations of the LCA

methodology to fully capture environmental sustainability and resilience of food value chains, a more complete set of metrics need to be developed to better compare underutilised crops various value chains with conventional ones.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sophie Saget: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David Styles:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Michael Williams:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix

Table A1

Leafy greens loss modelled during post-harvest transport.

	<i>CEA_UK</i>	<i>CEA_WindUK</i>	<i>Conv_UK*</i>	<i>Conv_ES</i>	<i>Conv_DesalES</i>	<i>Agro_PT</i>	<i>Agro_PT_sens</i>
Transport distance (km)	0	0	202	2096	2096	2821	3756
Post-harvest supply chain loss (%)	0	0	0.6	6.4	6.4	8.6	11.5
Post-harvest supply chain loss sensitivity analysis (%)	0	0	1.2	12.8	12.8	17.2	22.9

Table A2

General LCA results of the transport distance sensitivity analysis of the salad systems studied for 1 kg of delivered salad bag to the UK. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) is recorded in red and green, indicating environmental burdens that were higher or lower than those of the agroecological system, respectively. White indicates no statistical significance.

Name	Unit	Conv_UK	Conv_ES	Conv_DesalES	CEA_UK	CEA_WindUK	Agro_PT
Acidification	mol H ⁺ -Eq	0.007	0.011	0.012	0.029	0.006	0.006
Climate change (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ -Eq	0.37	0.66	0.77	5.22	0.57	0.58
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	14.1	33.3	43.3	87.8	20.3	9.9
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P-Eq	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0011	0.0002	0.0002
Eutrophication, marine	kg N-Eq	0.0020	0.0027	0.0029	0.0041	0.0006	0.0071
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N-Eq	0.022	0.032	0.034	0.022	0.006	0.021
Human toxicity,carcinogenic	CTUh	2.8E-10	4.7E-10	5.4E-10	2.8E-09	1.6E-09	1.8E-09
Human toxicity, non-carcinogenic	CTUh	8.7E-09	1.4E-08	1.6E-08	7.0E-08	1.7E-08	9.4E-09
Ionising radiation (human health)	kBq U235-Eq	0.03	0.06	0.10	4.37	0.03	0.02
Land use	dimensionless	35.1	54.2	38.1	54.1	4.6	12.3
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-Eq	3.8E-08	9.8E-08	1.1E-07	3.5E-07	2.6E-08	3.0E-08
Particulate matter	disease incidence	3.6E-08	6.7E-08	7.1E-08	1.1E-07	3.6E-08	1.5E-07
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC-Eq	0.002	0.004	0.004	0.011	0.002	0.003
Resource use, fossils	MJ, net calorific value	4.5	9.5	11.4	130.2	6.7	6.5
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb-Eq	3.0E-06	6.1E-06	8.0E-06	6.1E-05	1.2E-05	3.7E-06
Water use (user deprivation potential)	m ³ world eq. deprived	1.77	14.18	0.66	0.52	0.28	1.27

Table A3

General LCA results of the transport distance sensitivity analysis of the salad systems studied for 1 kg of delivered salad bag to the UK. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) is recorded in red and green, indicating environmental burdens that were higher or lower than those of the agroecological system, respectively. White indicates no statistical significance.

Name	Unit	Conv_U	Conv_E	Conv_DesalE	CEA_U	CEA_WindU	Agro_PT_se
		K	S	S	K	K	ns
Acidification	mol H ⁺ -Eq	0.007	0.011	0.012	0.029	0.006	0.007
Climate change (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ -Eq	0.37	0.66	0.77	5.22	0.57	0.9
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	14.1	33.3	43.3	87.8	20.3	14.1
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P-Eq	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0011	0.0002	2.0E-04
Eutrophication, marine	kg N-Eq	0.0020	0.0027	0.0029	0.0041	0.0006	0.008
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N-Eq	0.022	0.032	0.034	0.022	0.006	0.027
Human toxicity, carcinogenic	CTUh	2.8E-10	4.7E-10	5.4E-10	2.8E-09	1.6E-09	2.0E-09
Human toxicity, non-carcinogenic	CTUh	8.7E-09	1.4E-08	1.6E-08	7.0E-08	1.7E-08	1.4E-08
Ionising radiation (human health)	kBq U235-Eq	0.03	0.06	0.10	4.37	0.03	0.04
Land use	dimensionless	35.1	54.2	38.1	54.1	4.6	17.1
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-Eq	3.8E-08	9.8E-08	1.1E-07	3.5E-07	2.6E-08	9.5E-08
Particulate matter	disease incidence	3.6E-08	6.7E-08	7.1E-08	1.1E-07	3.6E-08	1.8E-07
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC-Eq	0.002	0.004	0.004	0.011	0.002	0.005
Resource use, fossils	MJ, net calorific value	4.5	9.5	11.4	130.2	6.7	11.2
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb-Eq	3.0E-06	6.1E-06	8.0E-06	6.1E-05	1.2E-05	4.7E-06
Water use (user deprivation potential)	m ³ world eq. deprived	1.77	14.18	0.66	0.52	0.28	1.4

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